

STUDIES IN THE NEGATIVELY CHARGED COLLOIDAL SOLUTIONS OF
VARIOUS FERRIC SALTS. PART III. NEGATIVELY CHARGED
MIXED SOL OF FERRIC OXIDE AND FERRIC MOLYBDATE

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Negatively charged ferric molybdate sols have been prepared by peptising freshly precipitated ferric molybdate by caustic soda in presence of glucose and glycerine. The sols peptised by glucose and glycerine have respectively the compositions $21\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $28\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3 \cdot 30\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Various characteristics of the sols have been investigated.

Graham (*Annalen*, 1865, 135, 65) long ago recognised the existence of a sol of molybdic acid which he prepared by dialysis of a solution of sodium molybdate acidified with a slight excess of hydrochloric acid. The semi-colloidal nature of molybdic acid was studied by Bruni and Pappada (*Gazzetta*, 1901, 31, 1, 244), Wöhler and Engels (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1910, 1, 466), and Linder and Picton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1892, 61, 155). Dhar and collaborators (*Kolloid Z.*, 1927, 42, 124; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, 190, 421) studied the viscosity of colloidal solutions of molybdic acid under different conditions. The colloidal nature of heavy metal molybdates has not been much studied. Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1916, 20, 640) obtained colloidal lead molybdate by precipitating the salt and washing with hot water. Dhar and Ghosh (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, 152, 405) found that lead molybdate was peptised by ammonium molybdate. Prakash and Dhar (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 587; 1930, 7, 367) obtained the hydrogels of zirconium, thorium and stannic molybdate and Varma and Prakash (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1932, 205, 241) investigated the peptisation of ferric molybdate by ferric chloride in presence of various peptising agents such as glucose, glycerine and urea. The sols and gels studied so far were positively charged and no work appears to have been done on the negatively charged sol or gel of ferric molybdate.

In previous communications of this series (Mushran and Prakash, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 111, 391), the preparation, composition and various other characteristics of negatively charged colloidal solutions of ferric vanadate and borate were described. In this paper, the detailed study of the properties and composition of negatively charged ferric molybdate sols has been described.

When potassium molybdate is added to a ferric chloride solution, a yellowish white precipitate of ferric molybdate is obtained. We have observed that this precipitate of ferric molybdate can be dispersed by suitable concentrations of a caustic soda solution in presence of glucose or glycerine to give a bright red sol of ferric molybdate which can be shown by electrophoresis to be negatively charged. An idea of the peptisation can be had from the following figures :

Ferric chloride solution (1.5-2.5 c.c. containing 30.36 g. of Fe_2O_3 per litre) when mixed with 1.0 to 2.0 c.c. of a 10% potassium molybdate solution in presence of 0.4 to 3.0 c.c. of 20% glucose solution requires 2.0 to 4.2 c.c. of *N*-NaOH solution (total volume 10 c.c.) to bring about the complete peptisation in half an hour.

The same ferric chloride solution (1.0-2.5 c.c.) when mixed with 1.0 to 2.0 c.c. of 10% potassium molybdate solution in presence of 0.2 to 3.0 c.c. of glycerine requires 1.4 to 3.4 c.c. of *N*-NaOH solution (total volume 10 c.c.) to bring about the complete peptisation in half an hour.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sol A was prepared by mixing 50 c.c. of a ferric chloride solution (containing 30.36 g. of Fe_2O_3 per litre), 50 c.c. of 10% potassium molybdate solution, 25 c.c. of 20% glucose solution and 100 c.c. of *N*-NaOH solution. The total volume was raised to 250 c.c. The sol was dialysed for five days.

Sol B was prepared by mixing 100 c.c. of the same ferric chloride solution, 100 c.c. of 10% potassium molybdate solution, 100 c.c. of glycerine and 170 c.c. of *N*-NaOH solution. The total volume was raised to 500 c.c. The sol was dialysed for three days.

Compositions of the Sols

The amount of iron in a known volume of the sol was estimated by the use of the reagent cupferron (*vide* Part II of this series). The molybdate was estimated as MoO_3 . For this, a known volume of the sol was dissolved in Merck's hydrochloric acid in a small pressure bottle and the solution was saturated in the cold with hydrogen sulphide. The bottle was then closed, heated on a water-bath until the precipitate completely settled. The precipitate was filtered off when it became cold, and was washed with dilute acid solution and finally with alcohol until the acid was completely removed. The moist filter paper with the solid was placed in a silica crucible and dried on a water-bath. The crucible was covered and heated very carefully over a small flame. The cover was then removed, the carbon was burnt off from the sides of the crucible at as low a temperature as possible, and by raising the temperature gradually, the sulphide was changed to the oxide and weighed. This gave the value of the total molybdate. In order to find out how much of the molybdate was in the combined state with iron, a known volume of the sol was coagulated by potassium chloride, the total coagulum was collected, washed and estimated as MoO_3 . The coagula have also been obtained cataphoretically and the concordance of the results shows that the equilibrium between the free and the combined molybdate is not appreciably altered. The combined iron corresponding to this amount of molybdate is calculated on the assumption that the ferric molybdate is $\text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3$. The rest of the iron is present as hydrated ferric oxide. From the ratio of the free to the combined iron, the empirical formula of the sol is calculated. The viscosity of the sol was measured by Ostwald's method at 30° and the amount of bound water was calculated from Hatscheck's equation (*vide* Part I of this series).

The sols were coagulated by KCl, centrifuged and the p_H values of the supernatant aqueous layers were determined using the hydrogen electrode. The p_H values obtained were 7.39 for sol A and 7.64 for sol B.

Conductivity Measurements

In the following tables are recorded the conductivities of these sols at various dilutions, at various temperatures and at different stages of ageing.

TABLE I

Per litre.	Sol A		Sol B	
	Glucose sol	Glycerine sol	Per litre.	
Total iron	3.0070 g.	2.9976 g.	Combined iron	0.1370
Total molybdate (MoO ₃)	0.8400	0.9050	Free iron	2.8700 g.
Combined molybdate (MoO ₃)	0.5300	0.4000	Viscosity of sol (30°)	0.00828
Free molybdate (MoO ₃)	0.3100	0.5050	Viscosity of water (30°)	0.00803
Empirical formula	21Fe ₂ O ₃ ·Fe ₃ (MoO ₄) ₃ ·H ₂ O.		Water, bound	0.02752
	28Fe ₂ O ₃ ·Fe ₃ (MoO ₄) ₃ ·30H ₂ O			0.49530

* The high viscosities are due to the presence of a sufficient concentration of free glycerine, as the sol could not be dialysed for long. The instability of the sol also contributed towards this end.

TABLE IIA

Sp. conductivity at different dilutions (30°)

Dilutions.	Sp. conductivity × 10 ⁴ mho.		Dilutions.	Sp. conductivity × 10 ⁴ mho.	
	Sol A	Sol B		Sol A	Sol B
Original sol (X)	15.50	27.19	X/2	7.98	14.50
5X/6	12.71	23.12	X/3	5.54	10.10
2X/3	10.23	18.54	X/6	2.72	5.57

TABLE IIB

Sp. Conductivity on ageing (30°)

Date.	Sp. conductivity × 10 ⁴ mho.		Date.	Sp. conductivity × 10 ⁴ mho.	
	Sol A	Sol B		Sol A	Sol B
9.2.45	15.50	27.19	23.2.45	..	The sol settles
12.2.45	..	27.40	4.3.45	15.69	down
15.2.45	15.58	27.62	4.4.45	15.78	
18.2.45	..	27.66	4.5.45	15.91	

TABLE IIC

Sp. conductivity at different temperatures

Temp.	Sol A		Diff. per 5°.	Sol B	
	Sp. condy. × 10 ⁴ mho.			Sp. condy. × 10 ⁴ mho.	Diff. per 5°.
40°	18.50		1.49	32.50	2.66
35°	17.01		1.51	29.84	2.65
30°	15.50		1.37	27.19	2.63
25°	14.13		1.53	24.56	2.67
20°	12.60		1.39	21.89	2.89
15°	11.21			19.00	
Temp. of zero conductance (extrapolated)	—16.0°				—20.0°
Temperature coefficient per 1°	0.29				0.54

From the results recorded in the tables above it will be seen that in the case of sol A, the conductivities are proportional to the dilutions in the beginning and as the sol is further diluted, the conductivities do not decrease in the same proportion as the dilutions, suggesting hydrolysis of the sol at higher dilutions; in the case of sol B, the conductivities are not proportional to the dilutions at any dilution of the sol, suggesting marked hydrolysis of the sol on dilution. The conductivities of the sols increase on ageing. The sp. conductivity-temperature graphs are straight lines. The temperatures of zero conductance of the sols lie between -16.0° and -20.0° .

Extinction Coefficients of the Sols

Extinction coefficients were determined using Nutting's spectrophotometer at different dilutions and at different wave-lengths (X stands for the original undiluted sol).

TABLE III

Sol A						
Wave-length.	Dilutions					
	X	X/2	X/4	X/8	X/16	
5000Å	..	..	2.35	1.19	0.60	
5200	..	3.30	1.66	0.84	0.43	
5400	..	2.31	1.16	0.59	0.30	
5600	3.17	1.59	0.79	0.40	0.21	
5800	2.20	1.10	0.56	0.28	0.16	
6000	1.67	0.84	0.42	0.21	0.11	
6200	1.12	0.56	0.28	0.15	0.08	
6400	0.98	0.49	0.25	0.13	0.07	

Sol B									
Wave-length	Dilutions				Wave-length	Dilutions			
	X	X/2	X/4	X/8		X	X/2	X/4	X/8
4800Å	..	2.83	2.04	1.24	5800Å	1.05	0.65	0.41	0.30
5000	3.73	2.14	1.41	0.82	6000	0.72	0.45	0.30	0.27
5200	3.00	1.75	0.92	0.54	6200	0.53	0.38	0.28	0.23
5400	2.25	1.32	0.76	0.46	6400	0.40	0.30	0.24	0.18
5600	1.55	0.95	0.55	0.37					

It will be seen from the above table that in the case of sol A Beer's law is followed for dilutions X/2 and X/4 but for dilutions X/8 and X/16 there are slight discrepancies. In the case of sol B Beer's law is not followed for any dilution of the sol; the extinction coefficients are always greater than those computed on the basis of dilution. The hydrolysis of ferric molybdate at different dilutions has caused these deviations. Our results on the conductivities at different dilutions (Table II) also show similar behaviour.

Coagulation of the Sols

In the following table are recorded the minimum amounts of electrolytes necessary to coagulate 1 c.c. of the sols in a total volume of 10 c.c., the time allowed in each case being 30 minutes.

TABLE IV

Electrolytes.	Amount for coagulation		Electrolytes.	Amount for coagulation	
	Sol A.	Sol B.		Sol A.	Sol B.
N/2-NaCl	4.7 c.c.	0.7 c.c.	N/250-Ba(NO ₃) ₂	4.8 c.c.	0.9 c.c.
N/2-KCl	4.5	0.5	N/250-Sr(NO ₃) ₂	5.0	1.2
N/2-KNO ₃	4.5	0.5	N/250-AlCl ₃	2.9	0.5
N/2-KBr	4.5	0.5			

The coagulating powers of the ions thus fall in the following series :

The effect of dilution on the coagulation values has also been investigated. Total volume was 10 c.c.

TABLE V

Electrolytes.	Amount necessary for coagulation of					
	1 c.c.	2 c.c.	3 c.c.	1 c.c.	2 c.c.	3 c.c.
	Sol A			Sol B		
N/2-NaCl	4.70	4.85	4.99	0.70	0.80	1.10
N/2-KCl	4.50	4.60	4.70	0.50	0.60	0.70
N/2-KNO ₃	4.50	4.60	4.70	0.50	0.60	0.70

From Tables IV and V it is evident that the sols obey the Schulze-Hardy rule for coagulation with electrolytes, and that they show the normal behaviour with dilution.

Positively Charged Ferric Molybdate Sol

It was reported by Varma and Prakash (*loc. cit.*) that the precipitate obtained by adding potassium molybdate to ferric chloride was only slightly peptised by ferric chloride alone to give a positively charged sol of ferric molybdate, but in presence of glucose, the peptisation occurred to a remarkable extent. In Table VI are shown our results on the composition of positively charged ferric molybdate sol.

The sol under investigation was prepared by mixing 40 c.c. of a ferric chloride solution (corresponding to 69.84 g. of Fe₂O₃ per litre), 25 c.c. of 20% glucose solution and 15 c.c. of 10% potassium molybdate solution. The mixture was vigorously shaken, filtered, and the filtrate was kept in a parchment bag and then allowed to dialyse. It was observed that the sol could not stand much dialysis, as in the course of twelve hours it became opalescent and very viscous and finally settled down. The sol was therefore dialysed for six hours and was then transferred to a Jena bottle. Estimations for iron and molybdate were made exactly in the same way as in the case of the negatively charged ferric molybdate sol.

TABLE VI

Per litre.		Per litre.	
Total iron	16.4638 g.	Viscosity of sol (30°) ..	0.00876 g.
Combined molybdate (MoO ₃) ..	9.7000	Viscosity of water (30°) ..	0.00803
Combined iron	2.5080	Water, bound	0.5786
Free iron	13.9558	Empirical formula ..	11Fe ₂ O ₃ ·2Fe ₂ (MoO ₄) ₃ ·3H ₂ O
Sol contained 15.8620g. of chloride ions per litre.			

DISCUSSION

According to Scheele a solution of ferric chloride gives a brown precipitate when treated with potassium molybdate. The analysis of this precipitate given by Marckwald ("Uber die Molybdate des Kobalts, Nickels, Mangans, Eisens, Chroms, und Aluminiums," Berlin, 1895) corresponds to $\text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3$. The precipitate appears according to the following equation :

We have observed that the precipitated ferric molybdate, though not easily peptised by caustic soda alone, goes to form a clear red sol if peptised in presence of glucose or glycerine. During the course of peptisation in presence of caustic soda, a part of the ferric molybdate may undergo hydrolysis according to the following reaction :

A further hydrolysis of ferric oxide-ferric molybdate complex may occur during dialysis also yielding a higher content of ferric oxide :

The composition of the sols analysed are given below :

Negatively charged : $21\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (glucose sol).

$28\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3 \cdot 30\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (glycerine sol).

Positively charged : $11\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{Fe}_2(\text{MoO}_4)_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

From the compositions given here it is clear that the positively charged sol contains a higher proportion of ferric molybdate than the negatively charged sols. The negatively charged sols are prepared mainly in the alkaline medium. Even after dialysis of the sols, the p_{H} of the supernatant aqueous layers, obtained after the coagulation of the sols with electrolytes, lie between 7.39 and 7.64. The sols prepared are sufficiently alkaline. This accounts for the larger proportion of ferric oxide in the negatively charged sols.

It will be interesting to discuss the temperature coefficients of conductivity of the negatively charged ferric molybdate sols. The temperature coefficients per 1° and the conductances at 35° are given below.

	Condy. at 35°	Temp. coeff.
Glucose sol (A)	17.01×10^{-4} mhos	0.29
Glycerine sol (B)	29.94	0.54

The temperature coefficient of sol A is thus 1.7% of the conductance at 35° and of sol B is 1.8% of the conductance at 35°. The temperature coefficients per 1° are therefore always less than 2% of the conductances at 35°.

CONCLUSION

Various characteristics of negatively charged ferric molybdate sols have been studied and from the results recorded in the foregoing tables the following observations may be summarised :

(i) The electrical conductivity of the 'glucose sol' is proportional to dilution in the beginning and as the sol is further diluted, the conductivities do not decrease in the same proportion as the dilution, suggesting hydrolysis of the sol at higher dilutions.

(ii) The electrical conductivity of the 'glycerine sol' is not proportional to dilution for any dilution of the sol, suggesting marked hydrolysis of the sol on dilution.

(iii) The electrical conductivities of the sols are linear functions of temperatures. The temperatures of zero conductance lie between -16.0° and -20.0° .

(iv) The temperature coefficients of conductivity per 1° of the sols are always less than 2% of the conductances at 35° .

(v) The conductivities of the sols increase on ageing.

(vi) The extinction coefficients of the glucose sol are proportional to dilution in the beginning and as the sol is further diluted, the extinction coefficients do not decrease proportionately with dilution.

(vii) The extinction coefficients of the glycerine sol do not decrease in the same proportion as dilution. The product of extinction coefficient and dilution is not constant. It shows a gradual increase as the dilution progresses.

(viii) The sols obey the Schulze-Hardy rule for coagulation with electrolytes. They show the normal behaviour on dilution.

(ix) The p_{H} values of the dispersion medium lie between 7.39 and 7.64 showing that the sols are slightly basic owing to the stabilising hydroxide ions.